

FACTORS OF SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETING EFFICIENCY

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Annotation

This article discusses the factors of simultaneous interpreting efficiency. The article consists of an on-demand annotation, keywords, introduction, main part, conclusion and a list of references.

Keywords: simultaneous, interpretation, challenges, efficiency, factors, translation, difference, similarities

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются факторы эффективности синхронного перевода. Статья состоит из аннотации по запросу, ключевых слов, введения, основной части, заключения и списка литературы.

Ключевые слова: синхронный перевод, проблемы, эффективность, факторы, перевод, различие, сходство

Simultaneous interpreting (SI) is one of the most complex language tasks imaginable. During SI one has to listen to and comprehend the input utterance in one language, keep it in working memory until it has been recoded and can be produced in the other language, and produce the translation of an earlier part of the input, all of this at the same time. Thus, language comprehension and production take place simultaneously in different languages. In this chapter we discuss simultaneous interpreting from a cognitive perspective. The unique characteristics of this task and comparisons with other, similar, tasks illustrate the demanding nature of SI. Several factors influence SI performance, including the listening conditions and the language combination involved. We discuss some processing aspects of SI, such as the control of languages and language recoding. We ask whether experience in interpreting is related to some special capabilities and discuss possible cognitive sub-skills of SI,

such as exceptional memory skills. Finally, we discuss the implications of SI for theories of language production.

When people are faced with a foreign-language barrier, the usual way around it is to find someone who speaks both languages to translate for them. Translation involves rephrasing a message expressed in one language – the source language – into another language – the target language. The term translation is often used in a broad sense, to refer to any way in which a fragment of source language can be turned into the analogous target language fragment, irrespective of input and output modality. To distinguish explicitly between different types of translation, in this chapter the term is generally used in its narrow sense. It then refers to text-to-text translation and contrasts with interpreting, which typically involves the verbal rephrasing of a source language utterance into a target language utterance. From a cognitive perspective it is important to distinguish between translation and interpreting because they are likely to engage different cognitive processes

Simultaneous interpreting (SI), sometimes called conference interpreting, can be argued to be one of the most complex language tasks imaginable because many processes take place at the same time. New input is continuously presented while the interpreter is involved simultaneously in comprehending that input and storing segments of it in memory. At the same time, an earlier segment has to be reformulated mentally into the target language and an even earlier segment has to be articulated. This complexity makes the study of simultaneous interpreting a challenging enterprise. If we are to understand fully how this task is performed, the separate research areas of language comprehension and language production, bilingualism, discourse processing, memory, attention, expertise, and complex skill performance may all provide relevant insights and should therefore, ideally, all be taken into account.

On the other hand, the process of SI itself may inform theories and models within all these separate research fields. Models of bilingualism, for example, need to accommodate the fact that in interpreting two languages must be activated and controlled simultaneously, and theories of speech perception that assign articulation

a crucial role in comprehension should be reconciled with the fact that in SI production and comprehension are performed simultaneously.

The experimental study of simultaneous interpreting

In trying to understand SI, researchers have, in general, taken three different approaches. The first approach concerns the detailed study of the output of the interpreting process under varying circumstances. The second approach is to regard SI as a complex task and as such to compare it with other tasks to gain more insight about the relevant processing components. For example, interpreting is often compared with shadowing, which involves the immediate verbatim repetition of what is heard. Interpreting and shadowing are similar in that both tasks involve simultaneous listening and speaking, but they are different in that shadowing does not require the input to be transformed. The third approach regards SI as a complex skill and compares experienced professional interpreters with students learning SI or with untrained but proficient bilinguals. The hypothesis underlying this approach is that interpreters may possess specific task-relevant sub-skills. Superior processing in particular cognitive sub-skills would suggest that the interpreting experience itself may boost these skills or that interpreters are self-selected on the specific abilities required for performing the task adequately.

Research on interpreting has its own methodological problems. A critical issue is that professional interpreters do not abound so that an adequate sample for any given study cannot always be obtained, especially if a specific language combination is required. Many studies are therefore prone to a lack of statistical power, making it hard to draw general conclusions from the data.

Characteristics of simultaneous interpreting

One of the most salient features of SI is that two streams of speech have to be processed simultaneously: The input has to be understood and the output has to be produced. Note that this implies that interpreters have a split conceptual attention.

One conceptual focus is directed to understanding the input, the other focus is Simultaneous interpreting: A cognitive perspective on conceptualizing and producing an earlier part of the message. Past research suggests that interpreters

exploit natural pauses and hesitations in the source speech to reduce simultaneous processing to a minimum. In an analysis of the temporal characteristics of source and target delivery patterns, confirmed that interpreters proportionally speak more during pauses in the input than would be expected if the input and output patterns were independent. When taking this into account, about 70% of the time that interpreters are speaking, they are simultaneously listening to input. In other words, most of the time interpreters have to cope with simultaneous comprehension and production of language.

To conclude with, simultaneous interpreting (SI) is one of the most intricate language assignments possible. During SI one needs to pay attention to and appreciate the information expression in one language, keep it in working memory until it has been recoded and can be delivered in the other language, and produce the interpretation of a prior piece of the information, all of this simultaneously. Along these lines, language cognizance and creation happen all the while in various dialects.

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